

D5.3-Month 24-Report on dissemination, exploitation, sustainability, and public outreach of the COST Action CA22119

WG5: Dissemination and outreach

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1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable, prepared 24 months after the start of the Action, aims to report about the work done and the progress achieved by the HELIOS COST Action in terms of dissemination, exploitation, sustainability, and public outreach activities to strengthen the impact of research results and foster their translation into daily practice in line with the general principle that *“COST Actions shall make their best effort to inform all relevant stakeholders about the Action and Action results, to follow principles of Open Science and Open Access in dissemination, and to aim at the valorisation of their results by facilitating their uptake by the research and innovation community in Europe and beyond, and society at large”*.

Dissemination activities include sharing findings with relevant communities, such as scientists and industry professionals. **Exploitation** is a form of valorisation that involves applying these results to create tangible benefits, such as new products, processes or services, or influencing policy. Ensuring **sustainability** means guaranteeing that the benefits of the project's outcomes continue after the project ends, often through developing networks or enduring resources. **Public outreach** involves communicating project activities and results to the general public and other non-scientific stakeholders to raise awareness of the societal relevance of the research and foster public engagement.

This document therefore provides details about the contribution provided by working group 5 (WG5) “Dissemination and outreach” in translating HELIOS scientific progress into lasting impact for society, patients, and the scientific community. WG5 activities aim at achieving four main objectives, to be documented in three deliverables, details in table 1 and table 2 below.

Table 1 – WG5 objectives

Objective	Description	Status
5.1.	Dissemination, including development and maintenance of the Action website	Development and regular update of the HELIOS website (see also deliverable D5.1); publication of updated content; participation in international conferences; first open access publications
5.2	Exploitation and intellectual property rights management, including identification of SMEs and private companies that can join the Action or support it for future expansion and research projects	Initiated collaborations with industrial partners; short-term scientific mission (STSM) with clinical impact (nanopore sequencing); IPR rules defined in line with EU standards
5.3.	Public outreach	Created visual identity (logo, templates); launched and managed social media channels; started the newsletter; produced outreach materials (leaflet, brochures, infographics); organised awareness events with patients and civil society
5.4.	Sustainability plan, including identification of funding opportunities for sustaining research in haemoglobinopathies	Built first partnerships with companies through sponsorships and event support; established synergies with EU projects and submitted new proposals; engaged with networks and societies.

Table 2 – WG5 deliverables

Deliverable	Description	Month	Status
D5.1	Action website	3	Delivered
D5.2	Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (initial release & update)	6, 30	1 st release delivered
D5.3	Report on dissemination, exploitation, sustainability, and public outreach	24, 48	1 st release delivered

Finally, Table 3 provides an overview of the Science Communication Plan adopted by the HELIOS action and highlights the different scope of communication, dissemination and valorisation activities.

Table 3 – Science Communication Plan overview

	Communication	Dissemination	Valorisation
Objectives	Strengthen identity and visibility (logo, website, social media, newsletter)	Share results through publications, conferences, webinars	Transfer results into clinical/industrial applications and build partnerships
Expected Impact	Increased recognition and public awareness	Broader access and use of scientific outcomes	Socio-economic return and support to sustainability through industry
Audiences	General public, patients, civil society	Researchers, clinicians, policymakers	Industry, SMEs, venture capital, patient organisations
Languages	Non-specialist, accessible	Scientific, specialist	Technical and general
Channel and tools	Website, social media, newsletter, promotional materials	Publications, conferences (ASCAT, EHA, BSH), EU platforms	Industry events, Training Schools, STSMs, joint publications

2. COMMUNICATION AND PUBLIC OUTREACH

2.1 COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES

During the first 24 months, HELIOS has advanced the goals set out in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan by establishing a strong brand identity and developing a common narrative that enables the network to communicate with one voice. Consistency in tone and style has been achieved through the creation of a project logo, the selection of a dedicated font, and the design of standardized templates, including HELIOS-branded PowerPoint slides and letterhead.

To engage both specialist and general audiences, the network has developed and promoted several social media campaigns, such as those for International Thalassaemia Day and the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, along with awareness-raising posts on new therapies (e.g., Casgevy approval). These activities reflect HELIOS’s commitment to engaging diverse audiences, increasing awareness of issues relevant to CA22119 and haemoglobinopathies in general, and promoting patient-centred information.

HELIOS has also played an active role in major scientific events to expand its outreach. In 2024 and 2025, the network hosted a booth and organized a dedicated session at ASCAT, one of the largest international conferences on haemoglobinopathies, which brought together researchers, clinicians, and patients. These activities resulted in numerous new memberships and high engagement at the booth. At the same event, HELIOS representatives contributed to a panel discussion on the initiative and delivered an oral

presentation showcasing the network's achievements. Further dissemination activities were carried out at additional events, including the Cyprus Thalassemia Conference.

2.2 EXPECTED IMPACT OF COMMUNICATION

The aim of effective communication is to make the outcomes and benefits of scientific collaboration visible to the general public.

Through its website, social media channels (LinkedIn, Instagram), and open events, HELIOS seeks to clearly and accessibly convey how the activities, awareness campaigns, guidelines, and trainings developed by the network can positively impact patients and society at large.

While initial activities have primarily reached specialists, patient advocacy groups, and representatives who follow HELIOS on social media, future work will intensify engagement with civil society and non-specialist audiences, leveraging success stories, interactive content, and cross-platform promotion.

2.3 COMMUNICATION AUDIENCES AND LANGUAGE

HELIOS's communication activities, while initially oriented toward a specialist audience, have progressively adopted differentiated language and formats to reach diverse stakeholders. Scientific terminology has been used in conferences, events, and reports on Zenodo for researchers and policymakers, while lay and accessible language has been consistently applied across social media channels and the project website. This approach ensures inclusiveness, engagement, and wider dissemination of results, making them accessible both to experts and the broader public.

In line with its commitment to transparency and open access, HELIOS makes all reports and policies publicly available through both the Zenodo open-access repository and the HELIOS website, enabling stakeholders, depending on the sensitivity of the content, to freely consult and reuse the material.

2.4 COMMUNICATION CHANNELS AND TOOLS

2.4.1 ACTION WEBSITE

All communication activities and initiatives are consistently published in English and disseminated through the web portal developed under the framework of WG5.

The project website (www.heliosaction.eu) serves as the primary reference point for information on the project, providing summaries of key scientific results and promoting dissemination and training activities.

In recent months, the site has been further enriched with project news and blog entries, currently featuring eight news items and nine HELIOS event testimonials. New sections have been introduced, including one dedicated to the HELIOS Inclusiveness and Equality Plan, as well as a comprehensive webinars section containing registration forms for upcoming events and links to recordings of past sessions. Several sections have been restructured to enhance navigation and improve user experience, ensuring access to more complete and up-to-date content. In addition, content has been optimized for SEO, and statistical tools have been implemented to monitor website traffic.

During the first two years, the HELIOS website proved to be an effective communication tool, reaching more than 1,100 users across all continents and generating over 3,000 interactions with different materials available online (Figure 1). The majority of users are English speakers, confirming the group's choice of English as the main language for communication.

Website analytics for the period September 2024 – September 2025 are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: HELIOS CA22119 Website Latest (Sept 2024-Sept 2025) Analytics

2.4.2 SOCIAL NETWORKS

HELIOS has chosen to use various social media platforms with the goal of reaching different types of audiences.

Table 4 – HELIOS Action social media platforms

Social Media	Target Audience	Current Network
Facebook	Non-specialist users, including dedicated groups, patients/families, and parent associations	235 followers
Instagram	Non-specialist users, to be reached through project-related images and videos	42 followers
Twitter	Community platform to share project information, retweet, and start live discussions	43 followers
LinkedIn	Professionals and companies seeking specialized content, researchers potentially interested in joining the HELIOS network	337 followers

YouTube	Very broad audience	23 subscribers
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The following sections present main KPIs for each social channel:

- **number of contents published;**
- **reach:** the number of monthly visits, that is the total number of unique accounts we have reached with our content;
- **impressions,** meaning the total number of times the post has been viewed through re-shares, saves, or comments (even if the same people see the same content 10 times);
- **growth of followers,** meaning the number of people who regularly follow our content.

Please note that analytics are not available for social channel X. For Instagram, they are only partially available.

→ Facebook

1. Channel opened in March 2024
2. 92 posts published from April 2024 to September 2025: 53 in 2024, 39 in 2025
3. Facebook reach and impressions from March 2024 to September 2025

Figure 2: HELIOS CA22119 – Facebook Analytics Report (Mar 2024 – Sep 2025)

4. Facebook growth of followers from March 2024 to September 2025

Figure 3: HELIOS CA22119 – Facebook Follower Growth Analytics (Mar 2024 – Sep 2025)

→ **Instagram**

1. Channel opened in March 2024
2. 77 posts published from April 2024 to September 2025: 44 in 2024, 33 in 2025
3. Instagram reach and impressions from March 2024 to September 2025

Figure 4: HELIOS CA22119 – Instagram Analytics Report (Mar 2024 – Sep 2025)

4. Instagram growth of followers from March 2024 to September 2025: data not available

→ **LinkedIn**

1. Channel opened in March 2024
2. 111 posts published from April 2024 to September 2025: 53 in 2024, 58 posts in 2025
3. LinkedIn reach and impressions from March 2024 to September 2025

Figure 5: HELIOS CA22119 – LinkedIn Analytics Report (Mar 2024 – Sep 2025)

4. LinkedIn growth of followers from March 2024 to September 2025

Figure 6: HELIOS CA22119 – LinkedIn Follower Growth Analytics (Mar 2024 – Sep 2025)

→ YouTube

1. Channel opened in March 2024
2. 37 videos published from April 2024 to September 2025: 17 in 2024, 20 post in 2025
3. YouTube views and impressions up to September 2025

Figure 7: HELIOS CA22119 – YouTube Analytics Report (Mar 2024 – Sept 2025)

4. YouTube growth of followers from March 2024 to September 2025

Figure 8: HELIOS CA22119 – YouTube Follower Growth Analytics (Mar 2024 – Sept 2025)

2.4.3 ZENODO ACCOUNT

As part of its dissemination and communication strategy, the HELIOS COST Action has created an account on [Zenodo](#), an open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. Zenodo provides a trusted platform for researchers, networks, and projects to share a wide range of outputs, including publications, datasets, presentations, software, and other research materials, with a global audience. Through our HELIOS Zenodo account, we make all relevant policies, working documents, guidelines, reports, and other outputs openly accessible to all audiences and interested stakeholders. This ensures transparency, supports knowledge exchange, and maximizes the long-term visibility and impact of the Action's work. In total, HELIOS reports on Zenodo account have more than 215 views, which shows that there is an interest regarding our action's results.

2.4.4 YOUNG RESEARCH INVESTIGATORS MONTHLY DISCUSSION CLUB

The monthly discussion club has been created and advertised among the members of the action. It is a scientific online meeting specifically targeting the educational development needs of Young Research Investigators (YRIs). YRIs have the chance to present the current status and results of scientific work on haemoglobinopathies to the network but also discuss new ideas, interact with experts of the field, disseminate their work, and establish new connections and collaborations.

Moreover, it includes lectures given by the researchers who have been granted the funds for a short-term scientific mission (STSM). These researchers can share with the network their experience, challenges and achievements of the STSM, along with the learning outcomes of the experience. It is regularly held once a month, in an online format, to enable wide participation.

2.4.5 INVITED SPEAKER SERIES (MONTHLY RECURRENCE)

The invited speaker series features monthly talks delivered by invited speakers, organised by Ms Stephanie Muth (Resonance Health). The speakers are selected based on their wide expertise on their field, as regards haemoglobinopathies, and on the basis of the selection of recently published articles that might be of interest to the action members on novel and intriguing findings on haemoglobinopathies are invited to present their work to the HELIOS network.

The series invites experts from outside the HELIOS network, spanning all fields related to haemoglobinopathies, including the clinical, private, research, diagnostic, and computer science sectors. This approach broadens the network's reach, engages a wider community of specialists, and raises awareness of the Action's activities. It also facilitates the dissemination of knowledge and the exchange of cutting-edge developments in the field, including perspectives and expertise that may not yet exist within the network. It also helps the establishment of new contacts and potential collaborations for our members. The talks are delivered online on a monthly basis. They are free and open to register to anyone who is interested.

2.4.6 FAIR PRINCIPLES WEBINARS

In collaboration with the [HemaFAIR project](#) (EU Grant no. 101159589), the HELIOS network developed a series of webinars about the FAIR principles to address a gap in data management practices identified with the surveys conducted by HELIOS WG3 and WG4. The webinars hosted leading experts of the field who introduced the FAIR principles, explaining each aspect and how they can be practically applied in the haemoglobinopathy practices from research to the clinical field.

2.4.7 CLINICAL AND RESEARCH PATIENT MANAGEMENT WEBINARS

HELIOS WG2 developed a series of clinical webinars hosting prestige experts of the field to increase knowledge capacity on patients' management. The webinars started with talk on iron overload, discussing the progress through the years, routine diagnostic practises, treatments and special cases. It followed by a lecture on Vascular access modalities - Technical aspects of RCE (automatic and manual). The lecture went into the depths of red cell exchange technique, presenting cutting research and standardized practises from one the leading and specialized institutes in Spain. Finally, the last webinar discussed Alloimmunization and extensive blood typing (genotyping and phenotyping) - Differences in acute and chronic programs. An expert of the field, with long-standing experience discussed the importance of alloimmunization and extensive blood typing, different approaches and application in hospitals, and its implication when it is neglected on patients' lives.

WG5 has handled all the organizational and promotional aspects of the webinars, namely:

- creating registration forms on Microsoft Teams and on the HELIOS website;
- creating promotional posts for social media;
- sending out surveys to assess participants' satisfaction with each webinar;
- uploading webinar recordings to the HELIOS YouTube channel.

Table 5 shows details about the webinar series.

Table 5 –Webinar series

	Date	Presenter	#Attendees	HELIOS Attendees	Females	Males	YRIs	ITCs
Webinars								
Monthly Discussion Club	06/03/2024	Dr Mariana Isabel Neves Delgado-Zoom	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Monthly Discussion Club	04/09/2024	Monika Nogel-Ethical Crossroads and Social Tides: Navigating the Complexities of Gene Editing for Beta Thalassemia and Sickle Cell Disease in the European Union	30	28	17	11	9	14
Monthly Discussion Club	04/06/2024	Dr Giulia Reggiani: Long-term effects of disease-modifying and disease curative therapies on organ damage in sickle cell disease	21	20	17	3	13	12
Monthly Discussion Club	17/09/2024	Maria Xenophontos: Enhancing structural Haemoglobin variant annotation and data quality	23	22	19	3	14	19
Monthly Discussion Club	08/10/2024	Florentia Romanou: Long-read-amplicon haplotyping for β -thalassaemia preimplantation genetic testing for couples with no additional family members	35	35	25	10	27	29
Monthly Discussion Club	03/12/2024	Giulia Ferrari: Monocentric Retrospective Study: Osteonecrosis of the Humeral Head in Sickle Cell Disease in a Pediatric Cohort	28	27	21	6	18	18
Invited Speaker	23/10/2024	The genetic dissection of foetal haemoglobin persistence in sickle cell disease in Nigeria	41	24	16	8	15	12
Invited Speaker	13/11/2024	Costs and impact of disease in adults with sickle cell disease: a pilot study	21	16	14	2	11	6
Invited Speaker	18/12/2024	Gaps during paediatric to adult care transfer escalate acute resource utilisation in sickle cell disease	23	15	9	6	10	5
Invited Speaker	15/01/2025	Machine Learning-Based Prediction of Hemoglobinopathies Using Complete Blood Count Data	34	30	22	8	15	16
Invited Speaker	03/02/2025	UM171 enhances fitness and engraftment of gene-modified hematopoietic stem cells from patients with sickle cell disease	16	13	12	1	9	7
Invited Speaker	26/03/2025	From PIEZO1 to iron: bridging membrane mechanotransduction and red blood cell disorders	29	18	13	5	12	7
Invited Speaker	30/04/2025	Update on SickleInAfrica: a collaborative and multidimensional approach to conduct research and improve health	29	16	13	3	13	9
Invited Speaker	06/18/2025	Long-term outcomes of avascular necrosis in sickle cell disease using joint-specific patient-reported outcome measures: Results from a multicentre study	22	16	13	3	12	9

	Date	Presenter	#Attendees	HELIOS Attendees	Females	Males	YRIs	ITCs
Fair Principles	27/10/2024	Lecture 1: Introduction to HemaFAIR	40			0		
Fair Principles	27/11/2024	Lecture 2: Introduction to FAIR principles	30	22	15	7	13	19
Fair Principles	14/01/2025	Lecture 3: Biomedical Ontologies	36	29	20	9	16	18
Fair Principles	27/01/2025	Lecture 4: Conceptual Models	32	25	16	9	16	17
Fair Principles	11/02/2025	Lecture 5	29	20	14	6	12	11
Fair Principles	11/03/2025	Lecture 6	38	38	28	10	20	18
Fair Principles	27/03/2025	Lecture 7	21	21	14	7	12	12
Fair Principles	10/04/2025	Lecture 8	27	27	20	7	15	15
Clinical Webinar	06/04/2025	Lecture 1: Iron Overload	27	23	19	4	10	11
Clinical Webinar	17/6/25	Lecture 2: Vascular modalities	19	16	14	2	12	12
Clinical Webinar	19/6/25	Lecture 3: Blood Exchange	18	16	16	16	2	10
Training Events								
Molecular Training School Athens	17/4/24		34	34	14	20	16	24
FAIR Principle Training School	12-14/05/25		36	32	21	12	18	23
Events								
WG & MC Athens Meeting	15/4/24		54	54	33	21	23	36
Scientific Meeting at ASCAT	10/03/2024		29	29	17	12	11	18
WG1 event in Cyprus	15-16/05/25		8	8	6	2	2	4
ASCAT 2025	03/10/25		7	7	4	3	3	2
		Total	851	695	488	224	386	420
		Percentage	100%	82%	57%	26%	45%	49%

YRI = Young Research Investigators
ITCs = Inclusiveness Target Countries

2.4.8 NEWSLETTERS

A quarterly newsletter is being produced since May 2024 to keep the target audience updated on the project's status and results, as well as on current and future activities. The newsletter also helps promote events and maintain the interest of the target audience. The newsletter is written in English.

Table 6 – HELIOS Action newsletter issues

Newsletter	Month	Recipients	Opens	Clicks	Unsubscribed
1	May 2024	174	90	15	0
2	Sept 2024	200	104	13	0
3	Jan 2025	239	148	41	1
4	Sept 2025	248	143	95	0

3. DISSEMINATION OF ACTION RESULTS

3.1. DISSEMINATION OBJECTIVES

Over these 24 months, HELIOS has worked towards achieving the main dissemination objectives, primarily by sharing the results with the scientific community through the publication of project findings in open-source and peer-reviewed scientific journals. HELIOS is reaching out to stakeholders outside the project to disseminate new knowledge and raise awareness about the importance of research, while continuously encouraging participation in relevant external events where the project, its approaches and its results are presented in dedicated sessions.

3.2. DISSEMINATION EXPECTED IMPACT

HELIOS is working to make the Action's results a common good, through appropriate tools tailored to each type of recipient.

3.3. DISSEMINATION AUDIENCES AND LANGUAGES

Dissemination activities are targeted at an academic audience as well as stakeholders from industry and institutional sectors. Activities such as the webinar series are aimed at scientists, physicians, educators, students, and researchers. To this end, articles are published in scientific journals, and presentations are given at national and international conferences and workshops, seminars, and events, all disseminated through the project's web portal.

3.4. DISSEMINATION CHANNELS AND TOOLS

All HELIOS partners have been involved in dissemination activities to raise awareness about the project's goals and results.

Among the main communication strategies adopted are:

- Scientific presentations at national and international conferences and workshops
- Publications in scientific journals and at international scientific conferences

Below are the European and international conferences where scientific results were presented, along with the corresponding outputs:

Activity	Target	Outcome	Link
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1st scientific meeting (Oct. 24)	Groups that may use the results in their own work including peers, industry, stakeholders. Regarding policymakers, engage and share evidence-based results during the legislative process	Brochures and presentations.	-
ASCAT 2024 (Oct. 2024)	Researchers, academics, policymakers, industry professionals, and stakeholders	1 leaflet, 2 blog posts	https://ascatconferences.com/
Transcranial Doppler Training School (Sep 2025)	Medical experts	Many individuals outside the HELIOS network showed interest in the workshop, which featured both theoretical and practical sessions, leading to an increase in network membership.	-
ASCAT 2025 (planned to take place in Oct. 2025)	Researchers, academics, policymakers, industry professionals, and stakeholders	brochures and presentations.	https://ascatconferences.com/

The following table presents the related scientific publications:

Title	Type of publication	Journal/platform	DOI
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Loss of function variants in SUPT5H as a modifying factor in beta-thalassemia	Peer-reviewed, open-source article	International Journal of Molecular Sciences	https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms25168928
Genetic polymorphisms associated with fetal hemoglobin (HbF) levels and F-cell numbers: A systematic review of genome-wide association studies,	Peer-reviewed, open-source article	International Journal of Molecular Sciences	https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms252111408
Mapping Areas of Expertise and Educational Priorities for Hemoglobinopathy Care to improve comprehensive patient management and Quality of Life: Insights from Healthcare Professionals in the HELIOS COST Action	Peer-reviewed, open-source article	Blood Global Hematology	Accepted for publication
HELIOS- Working Group 2 Report on CRF Hemoglobinopathies	Zenodo, open-source, article/report	Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15182593
HELIOS Inclusiveness and Equality Plan	Zenodo, open-source, article/report	Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15308443
HELIOS Science Communication Plan	Zenodo, open-source, article/report	Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15308485

4. EXPLOITATION (VALORISATION) OF ACTION RESULTS

4.1. VALORISATION OBJECTIVES

HELIOS valorisation activities have pursued two main objectives: to create networking and knowledge-sharing opportunities with a wide range of stakeholders beyond the research community, and to develop a coherent marketing strategy to strengthen the project's

visibility. These objectives have guided interactions with incubators, venture capital, innovation ecosystems, policymakers, industry, SMEs, scientific societies, and civil society.

4.2. VALORISATION EXPECTED IMPACT

The expected impact was to ensure both direct and indirect return on public investment in research, transforming Action results into tangible value for society and healthcare systems. After two years, HELIOS has already achieved significant progress by facilitating the transfer of knowledge into clinical and industrial applications, exemplified by the introduction of nanopore sequencing through STSMs. Joint publications, guidelines and conference presentations have been initiated with academic and industrial partners, while the recurrent involvement of pharmaceutical and biotech companies has helped consolidate network sustainability. HELIOS has also strengthened European leadership in haemoglobinopathy research by connecting scientific societies, European networks, and patient organisations.

4.3. VALORISATION AUDIENCES AND LANGUAGES

Valorisation activities have engaged a broad and diverse audience, including researchers, clinicians, pharmaceutical and diagnostic companies, policymakers, patient organisations, and professional associations. Each group has been addressed with tailored approaches: technical and specialised language for academic and industrial stakeholders, and accessible communication for patients and civil society. Transparency and dissemination have been reinforced by providing open access to reports, datasets, and publications.

4.4. VALORISATION CHANNELS AND TOOLS

Valorisation has been implemented through scientific conferences, training schools, joint publications and capacity-building activities, which have promoted knowledge transfer and dialogue between academia and industry. A particularly significant role has been played by STSMs, which have enabled participants to acquire new techniques, access data and tools not available at their home institutions and foster interdisciplinary collaborations.

Event	Activity	Participating industry representatives
ASCAT Conference 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Booth• Dedicated HELIOS session• Panel discussion• Oral presentation	Pfizer, Vertex Pharmaceuticals, Agios Pharmaceuticals, Sanofi, Global Action Network for Sickle Cell & Other Inherited Blood Disorders, Nova Laboratories, Sickle Cell Society, British Society for Haematology, European Hematology Association
Working Group & Management Committee Meeting 2024	Supported/Sponsored the events	Agios Pharmaceuticals, Lab Supplies Scientific

Event	Activity	Participating industry representatives
Molecular research and diagnosis of hemoglobinopathies Training School 2024	Supported/Sponsored the events	Agios Pharmaceuticals, Lab Supplies Scientific
Survey development	AI in haematology	ERN-EuroBlooNet network, the network has also endorsed the HELIOS COST action
ASCAT Conference 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Booth • Dedicated HELIOS session • Panel discussion • Oral presentation 	Pfizer, Vertex Pharmaceuticals, Agios Pharmaceuticals, NovoNordisk, Sanofi, Global Action Network for Sickle Cell & Other Inherited Blood Disorders, Nova Laboratories, Sickle Cell Society, British Society for Haematology, European Hematology Association

5. SUSTAINABILITY OF THE ACTION

5.1. SUSTAINABILITY OBJECTIVES

The HELIOS sustainability strategy aims to ensure that results, collaborations, and knowledge developed during the Action continue to generate impact beyond the official duration of COST funding. It rests on three main pillars: engagement with companies, access to new research funding, and integration with networks and scientific societies.

5.2. ENGAGEMENT WITH COMPANIES

Dialogue with pharmaceutical and biotech companies, initiated during the first two years with Pfizer, Sanofi, Vertex, Agios and diagnostic SMEs, has already led to sponsorship and support for events and training schools. These interactions, developed at major international conferences, provide a solid foundation for more structured collaborations aimed at co-developing research and capacity-building initiatives.

5.3. FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES AND PARTNERSHIPS

HELIOS is actively seeking to leverage EU-funded programmes to extend and consolidate its activities. Collaboration with HemaFAIR enables the integration of FAIR principles into data management, promoting interoperability, training, and international exchanges. In parallel, proposals for CHAMP (2024), CHAMPSS (2025), and HOPE (2024) have been submitted addressing Horizon Europe and NIH calls. If funded, they will reinforce network activities by advancing clinical research, training, and shared data collection. These initiatives are a critical lever for ensuring continuity and expanding HELIOS impact beyond the COST Action period.

5.4. COLLABORATIONS WITH NETWORKS AND SCIENTIFIC SOCIETIES

HELIOS sustainability also relies on integration within established European and international networks. Collaborations are already active with the projects [ARISE](#) (African Research and Innovative Initiative for Sickle cell Education) and the [HemaFAIR](#) European Project, and networks like the International Hemoglobinopathy Research Network ([INHERENT](#)), [ERN-EuroBloodNet](#), and the [Radeep](#) network, through joint participation in conferences, workshops, and guideline development. These alliances strengthen project visibility and secure its continuity within a broader ecosystem of research and clinical practice.

6. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS AND NEXT STEPS

After two years of implementation, HELIOS has achieved significant milestones in building visibility, disseminating scientific results, and initiating collaborations with industry partners, European networks, and patient organisations. The project identity is now consolidated and recognisable, and the first tangible results of valorisation and networking demonstrate a growing potential for socio-economic impact.

In the next two years, the Action will focus on strengthening partnerships with companies, engaging in new European funding opportunities, and consolidating alliances with major scientific societies and international networks. The aim is to ensure the sustainability of activities, expand knowledge transfer capacity, and secure that the value generated by HELIOS continues to deliver benefits well beyond the lifetime of the COST Action.

With these perspectives, HELIOS positions itself not only as a research network, but as a stable and innovative ecosystem, capable of transforming scientific knowledge into concrete tools for public health and society.